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Title: Dyadic planning as a complementary process to individual planning: Physical activity in daily diaries of patients with pre-obesity or obesity

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Abstract

Objectives: Individual planning techniques are frequent intervention components in physical activity (PA) promotion, but it is yet undetermined whether interpersonal regulatory efforts such as dyadic planning contribute to their success. This study examines individual planning and dyadic planning as predictors of PA in persons with pre-obesity and obesity who seek outpatient treatment for intended weight loss.

Design: Intensive-longitudinal design with daily diaries.

Methods: One-hundred-and-twenty-seven patients with pre-obesity or obesity consulting an outpatient clinic for endocrinology took part in an 8-day daily diary study. This secondary analysis used multilevel models to explain daily self-reported PA. Planning categories were created and entered as same-day predictors (*no planning, dyadic planning only, both individual and dyadic planning*, reference category: individual planning only).

Results: On days with *no planning* at all, participants reported being less physically active than on days with individual planning only. While *dyadic planning only* did not emerge as a unique predictor, participants were more physically active when they *planned both individually and dyadically* as compared to planning only individually.

Discussion: Consistent with scant previous research, we find dyadic planning to be mainly a complementary strategy to individual planning. Day-to-day individual planning together with dyadic planning was linked to more PA than individual planning alone. Our findings indicate that including planning partners in PA promotion for individuals with pre-obesity and obesity intending weight loss may be promising.

Keywords: dyadic action planning, health, physical activity, individual planning, pre-obesity, obesity

Introduction

Physical activity (PA) is a target behaviour in lifestyle interventions for people with overweight because it increases energy expenditure which aids weight control and improves health (Bellicha et al., 2021; Pojednic et al., 2022). According to Wadden et al. (2020), PA only plays a minor role in short-term weight loss by increased energy expenditure. Its focus is rather on long-term maintenance of weight loss and health improvements, such as blood pressure reductions. Health improvements from PA could be particularly relevant for people with obesity (body mass index, BMI, $\geq 30\text{kg/m}^2$) who are, compared to people without obesity, at higher risk of cardiovascular disease (Hemmingsson et al., 2022), diabetes mellitus (Abdullah et al., 2010), certain cancers (Renehan et al., 2008), and depression (Pereira-Miranda et al., 2017). With a worldwide prevalence of obesity in adults of between 11% (men) and 15% (women; World Health Organization, 2022), trying to improve health and well-being through more PA seems a worthwhile goal.

Planning as a Potentially Modifiable Determinant of PA

Behaviour change towards regular PA is hard to achieve and maintain. One way to contribute to intervention development is to understand what processes determine PA, and thus identify potentially modifiable intervention targets. In addition to motivational factors that partially determine PA, theories such as the Health Action Process Approach (HAPA; Schwarzer, 2008) assume that volitional factors such as self-regulation play a role, especially when there are barriers. Individual (action) planning (or implementation intentions; Gollwitzer, 1999; Hagger & Luszczynska, 2014) facilitates behaviour through the activation of a mental representation of an if-then statement which holds a cue (the “when”/“where”) and the performance of a goal-behaviour, i.e. ‘when I wake up, then I will do 10 min of gymnastics’. Meta-analyses found evidence of an effect of individual planning on PA (Carraro & Gaudreau, 2013; Sheeran et al., 2024). Effect sizes of the link between individual planning and PA were stronger for spontaneously-occurring individual planning ($\phi = .41$) compared to experimental intervention

studies ($\phi = .37$; Carraro & Gaudreau, 2013). A systematic review of studies with lifestyle interventions for people with obesity had found the use of self-regulation skills (such as planning) as relevant mediators of successful PA promotion (Teixeira et al., 2015), especially in the short-term, however, these mediating effects were observed in an analysis combining individual planning with other self-regulatory mediators (e.g. self-monitoring).

Planning Dyadically: Social Resources in Day-To-Day Behaviour Change

Involving planning partners in obesity treatment might be advantageous: In an exercise-oriented weight loss trial where participants were encouraged to invite weight loss support-buddies, participants who had buddies with successful weight loss lost more weight themselves as compared to participants with buddies not losing weight or participants without support buddies (Gorin et al., 2005). Evidence from a systematic review suggests that health behaviour change interventions for couples might be more beneficial than individual interventions (Arden-Close & McGrath, 2017), as additional resources and dyadic regulation could complement individual efforts to self-regulate. Transactive goal dynamics theory (Fitzsimons et al., 2015) posits that close relationships form a system that self-regulates as a unit. When there are numerous, strong, and well-coordinated ties between goals, pursuits, and outcomes, dyad partners can have transactive gain by drawing from a shared pool of resources.

One way in which interpersonal goal pursuit could manifest in social exchanges is dyadic planning. In dyadic planning a target person and a planning partner create plans for the target person on where, when and how to perform a new behaviour (Burkert et al., 2011). It has been explored in dyads such as romantic partners (Buitenhuis et al., 2021; Katzenelenbogen et al., 2022; Keller, Wiedemann, et al., 2017; Knoll et al., 2017; Kulis et al., 2025) and parent-child dyads (Kulis et al., 2024; Szczuka et al., 2024). Its focus on one target person can be relevant for persons with chronic conditions who have to take up a new behaviour as part of the treatment plan (e.g. pelvic-floor exercise after prostatectomy; Burkert et al., 2011). Plans created in dyads as compared to alone might be of higher quality, as planning partners could

check feasibility of plans (Keller, Fleig, et al., 2017). Assumed mechanisms that underlie an effect of dyadic planning on health behaviours are social exchange processes such as social support, social control, and intraindividual processes such as heightened action control (Burkert et al., 2011; Knoll et al., 2017), or self-efficacy beliefs (Keller, Wiedemann, et al., 2017).

Evidence of dyadic planning interventions is heterogeneous: Kulis et al. (2022) found a small effect of a dyadic planning intervention on target person's PA after 6 months, compared to an individual planning control condition in an RCT. In contrast, 6-week and 1-year findings of an RCT with a dyadic planning condition tested against individual planning and an active control condition (Keller et al., 2020; Knoll et al., 2017) did not demonstrate higher PA in target persons. The heterogeneous evidence might stem from the differences in intervention dosage and/or determination of the role of target persons on the basis of health needs (Kulis et al., 2022) versus on the basis of randomization (Keller et al., 2020; Knoll et al., 2017).

Whereas some personal characteristics, dispositions, behaviour- and self-related cognitions determining health behaviour are stable, other determinants are highly time- and context-varying. The need to consider timing in health behaviour change and self-regulation in particular has been called for recently by scholars (Millar, 2017; Scholz, 2019). Daily links between individual planning and daily PA have been found in couples with overweight and obesity (Berli, Lüscher, et al., 2018). Social exchange strategies also seem to be time-varying. Berli, Bolger, et al. (2018) confirmed high intrapersonal variability in daily social support, which is one assumed mechanism underlying dyadic planning. Higher-than-usual daily social support was found to be related to higher PA in couples with overweight and obesity (Berli, Bolger, et al., 2018). This was also found in a sample of patients with type 2 diabetes and their spouses (Khan et al., 2013).

Dyadic planning, a social exchange strategy combining planning with social resources, has recently been examined as a predictor of individually-chosen goal pursuits in couples (e.g. improve academic performance, losing weight; Katzenelenbogen et al., 2022). The study

demonstrated that dyadic planning had mainly been used as “complementary strategy”, in addition to individual planning. Katzenelenbogen et al. (2022) found that the combination of dyadic planning with individual planning was a stronger predictor of goal progress compared to individual planning alone. The effects of dyadic planning have yet to be explored in patients with pre-obesity or obesity and for the target behaviour of daily PA.

Aims of the Study

The aim of the present study was to describe spontaneous individual and dyadic planning in the daily lives of patients with pre-obesity or obesity who consulted an endocrine outpatient clinic for intended weight loss. Another aim was to examine whether there were within-person links between individual and dyadic planning and daily PA. Lastly, we examined whether dyadic planning would be a unique predictor, in terms of predictive power. Specifically, we investigated how no planning and dyadic planning compared with individual planning as a reference category. By design, we did not limit the focus on a fixed planning partner, such as the romantic partner, but any planning partner (e.g., friends, family members, etc.) being part of the daily lives of the person. Our hypotheses were:

H1: On days with no planning, individuals are less physically active than on days with individual planning.

H2: On days with dyadic planning, individuals are more physically active than on days with individual planning.

H3: On days with dyadic planning combined with individual planning, individuals are more physically active than on days with individual planning only.

Materials & Methods

Design and Procedure

Data were collected as part of a longitudinal study with outpatients seen for obesity diagnostics and weight loss management at the former *[blinded for review]*, between May 2009 and September 2011. Trained research assistants approached patients after their consultation and invited them for participation in a prospective study across 6 months. From this larger study, we use only patients' baseline data, including medical information (BMI, comorbidities) from the consulting physician, and intensive-longitudinal data collected after study start for this secondary data analysis. Intensive-longitudinal study components were a daily diary for eight days after the study start, and additional assessment of PA using the SenseWear™ PRO 3 armband (BodyMedia, Pittsburgh, USA) for three days (Sunday to Tuesday). Participants did not receive compensation for participation. The institution's Research Ethics Board *[blinded for review]* approved the study.

This is a secondary analysis of data previously published by *[blinded for review]*, who focused on reporting changes in PA, energy expenditure and eating habits across the 6-month follow-up period. In summary, only 19% of participants had achieved substantial weight loss of >5% body weight. Self-reported unhealthy food consumption had decreased, but objectively assessed PA and energy expenditure levels were not kept up across the study period.

Inclusion criteria for patients with pre-obesity and obesity at the outpatient clinic were written informed consent to participate in the study and a medical indication for an increase in daily PA. Exclusion criteria were insufficient German language skills for study participation, hypercortisolism, conditions prohibiting daily PA, e.g., clinically relevant heart failure, severe osteoarthritis, limiting pulmonary diseases, or amputations. Of $N = 169$ patients who were invited to take part, nine declined. A total of $N = 160$ patients gave informed consent, were included in the study and provided data at baseline. Of those, $n = 127$ participated in the daily diary part of the study. Descriptive statistics on differences between the diary and non-diary

participants, who nevertheless participated in baseline assessments are reported in *Supplementary Material S1*. Participants who took part in the diary-part of the study were older, had a lower BMI, and had shorter relationship durations with their romantic partners.

Sample

Participants were on average $M(SD) = 41.78(14.10)$ years old and 78% were women. With an average of $M(SD) = 42.76(8.13)$ kg/m², their BMIs ranged between 28.12-64.27 kg/m². The obesity category of class III (≥ 40 kg/m²; Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, June 3, 2022) was met by 58% of participants. Twenty-one percent of participants had type 2 diabetes. Forty-six percent of participants had a high school diploma. Sixty-nine percent were in a romantic relationship of on average $M(SD) = 15.22(13.54)$ years. For 86% of participants, this was the first consultation at the outpatient clinic. Five participants had already undergone bariatric surgery in the past (e.g., gastric bypass, sleeve resection), between 1-8 months prior to the diary phase. In the course of their routine treatment, all participants would receive individualized dietary and physical activity advice by a dietician and other, individually-tailored weight loss treatment such as pharmacotherapy. At the time of the daily diary phase, participants had undergone no other treatment by the outpatient clinic.

Measures

Paper-pencil, end-of-day diaries in the German language were administered for eight days after the consultation at the clinic.

Daily Physical Activity (PA)

Daily PA in Metabolic Equivalents of Task (MET)-minutes/day was assessed via self-report. METs refer to an activity's energy expenditure in relation to body weight, with MET = 1 representing the energy expenditure during resting. Our measure of daily PA was adapted from the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) long version (Wanner et al., 2016). For walking, moderate activities, and vigorous activities in four life domains (transport, work, home and garden, leisure), participants entered the minutes they spent in those activity categories on

that day into a double-paged, 24h timeline. A similar “PA log book” daily diary was described in Hagströmer et al. (2006). Following the scoring protocol for the IPAQ (International Physical Activity Questionnaire team, 2005), we set any time span below 10 minutes to zero, and truncated records of total walking, total moderate and total vigorous activity minutes to 3 hours a day each. Days with more than 16 hours of activity were excluded as outliers. We then multiplied reported minutes per day with the respective MET-value of the activity (walking = 3.3 MET; moderate activities = 4.0 MET; vigorous activities = 8 MET; Ainsworth et al., 2011). A sum of MET-minutes for each day was computed. The outcome, daily PA, was winsorized to 5th/95th percentiles (Aguinis et al., 2013) to adjust for univariate outliers. To check for bias such as overestimation in our self-reported daily PA measure, we validated our measure with objective data. Energy expenditure indicators assessed by SenseWear armbands were used for partial validation of self-report-based daily PA through correlation coefficients. For details see *Supplementary Material S2*.

Individual Planning

Daily diaries assessed individual planning with two items, “Today, I planned ...”, (a) “...when, where and how I want to be physically active”, and (b) “...how I will be able to be physically active despite possible difficulties and barriers” (adapted from Burkert et al., 2011; Sniehotta et al., 2005). Answers were given on a 6-point Likert scale from 1 (*not at all true*) to 6 (*exactly true*). The reliability of the average two-item responses across days was $R_{kF} = .96$, and of day-to-day changes it was $R_{change} = .81$ (Cranford et al., 2006).

Dyadic Planning

Daily diaries assessed dyadic planning by two items, “Today, I planned with my partner ...”, (a) “...when, where and how I want to be physically active”, and (b) “... how I will be able to be physically active despite possible difficulties and barriers” (adapted from Burkert et al., 2011; Sniehotta et al., 2005). “My partner” referred to the respective planning partner on the specific day. The assessment allowed for varying planning partners and was not limited to romantic

partners, but any relationship type. Answers were given on a 6-point Likert scale from 1 (*not at all true*) to 6 (*exactly true*). The reliability of the average two-item responses across days was $R_{kF} = .96$, and of day-to-day changes it was $R_{\text{change}} = .85$ (Cranford et al., 2006). As additional descriptive information for each day, planning partners could be named. For descriptive results on planning partners, see *Supplementary Material S3*.

Statistical Analyses

All analyses were run in R (Version 4.3.1) and SPSS (Version 29). For descriptive statistics, between-person correlations for descriptive statistics were run as Pearson's correlations. Within-person correlations between study variables and covariate screening were analysed with the R-package *rncorr* (Bakdash & Marusich, 2017), to allow for the nested structure of days in individuals. To understand change and variation in the three central variables, unconditional growth models were calculated for linear and quadratic time trends (Singer & Willett, 2003). If models did not converge, the random effect for the quadratic time trend was omitted from the models.

For validation of the self-reported primary outcome (i.e., daily PA) with the objective SenseWear data, we matched data by date. Agreement between the two sources of PA/energy expenditure data was determined by Spearman's rho for person-means, and repeated-measures correlations for daily PA (*Supplementary Material S2*).

We also investigated possible dropout mechanisms such as (a) characteristics differing between the diary and the non-diary sample (see *Supplementary Material S1*) and (b) characteristics differing between diary-dropouts (i.e., partial diary reports with last diary entry on days 1-6) and diary-non-dropouts (partial or complete diary reports with last diary entry on days 7 or 8) by *t*-tests, or χ^2 -tests.

The analytic approach proposed by Katzenelenbogen et al. (2022) was applied to investigate daily associations of PA with both planning variables. First, we dichotomised scores, where the lowest response option, 1 (*not at all true*), was coded "no planning" (0). Any answer

above the lowest response option were scored as “some planning” (1). These dichotomized scores for individual and dyadic planning were combined in four categories: *No planning* (i.e., no individual and no dyadic planning), *individual planning only* (i.e., individual, but not dyadic planning), *dyadic planning only* (i.e., dyadic, but not individual planning), and *both individual and dyadic planning* (i.e., individual and dyadic planning). These categories were dummy-coded (0 = no; 1 = yes). In the following multilevel models, we used *individual planning only* as reference category. This approach became necessary, because we had encountered that dyadic planning had too rarely been used on its own which would have made moderation analyses with two continuous planning predictors difficult to compute.

The diary data were analysed using multilevel models with two levels (level 1: days, nested in level 2: persons) following recommendations by Bolger and Laurenceau (2013). Same-day, time-varying planning categories (*no planning*, *dyadic planning only*, *both individual and dyadic planning*) were separated into their within-person and between-person components using group-mean centering of the grand-mean centered raw scores (Bolger & Laurenceau, 2013). Between-person predictors indicated average planning deviations of a person across the diaries from the grand-mean. Within-person predictors indicated the fluctuations of a daily score from a person’s average. Among the fixed effects, we controlled for a linear time trend (centered at day 1). We specified a maximal random effects structure (Barr et al., 2013) where this was possible, depending on model convergence. Priority was given to planning variables in random-effects estimation. Random effects for a linear time trend and *dyadic planning only* had to be omitted due to model non-convergence, however. We specified a first-order autoregressive covariance structure (AR1) for the within-person level and used REML. Equations can be found in *Supplementary Material S4*.

Sensitivity analyses accounted for between-person level covariates (age, gender, BMI, type 2 diabetes, romantic relationship, mood/anxiety disorder, smoking, living alone, vocational training, without work) in a fully-controlled model (*Supplementary Material S5*). In part, the

covariates were derived from previous research, in part from covariate screening and dropout analyses. These additional between-person-only covariates were centered around their grand means. We also re-ran the models excluding four participants whose BMI ranged below the obesity cut-off of 30 (*Supplementary Material S6*).

Results

Dropout Analyses

The compliance rate for eight days of end-of-day diaries was 95%. Participants responded on average to $M(SD) = 7.57(1.33)$ diaries, ranging from 2-8 diaries. Participants who did not participate in diary assessments were younger, had a higher BMI, and were in shorter romantic relationships than participants who took part in diary assessments (see *Supplementary Material S1*). Participants who dropped out in the course of diary assessments were more likely to have trained at a vocational school ($\chi^2(1) = 6.71, p = .010$), have a chronic respiratory/lung condition ($\chi^2(1) = 4.25, p = .039$), and were more likely to be currently without work ($\chi^2(1) = 3.97, p = .046$).

Validation of Self-Reported Daily Physical Activity Data by Device-assessed Energy Expenditure

Correlations between person means for self-reported daily PA and three indicators of SenseWear-derived energy expenditure ranged between Spearman's $\rho = .33$ -.38 ($p < .001$) for non-exercise related activity thermogenesis, exercise-related activity thermogenesis, and mean MET. Within-person correlations between daily PA and daily SenseWear-derived energy expenditure ranged between $r = .29$ ($p < .001$; exercise-related activity thermogenesis), across $r = .39$ ($p < .001$; non-exercise-related activity thermogenesis), to $r = .43$ ($p < .001$; mean MET, see *Supplementary Material S2*).

Individual and Dyadic Planning: Descriptive Results and Change Models

Table 1 shows means, standard deviations, and intraclass correlation coefficients (ICC) for daily PA, individual planning and dyadic planning. For daily PA, 48% of variability was due to between-person variation. *Table 2* shows two-level models estimating change in the three central variables. Daily PA or individual planning indicated no significant linear or quadratic time trend across the eight days. There was a linear and a quadratic time trend for dyadic planning indicating a slight initial decrease, which was compensated by a u-shaped increase in dyadic

planning. Regarding between-person variation, there was substantial variation in starting points for daily PA, dyadic planning, and individual planning, but no, or just a marginally significant time effect for individual planning's variation in slopes ($p = .056$).

Participants planned individually on 59% of days ($M = 4.28$ out of 8 days, total $n = 926$ days valid data), and dyadically on 31% of days ($M = 2.01$ days, total $n = 825$ days). Daily individual and dyadic planning were highly correlated, $r = .52$ ($p < .001$). *Figure 1* displays frequencies of the four planning categories. The category of *dyadic planning only* held a mere 1% of observations which shows that dyadic planning was very rarely used as the only planning strategy (i.e., without individual planning).

Hypotheses Tests: Associations of Daily Physical Activity (MET-min/day) with Planning

We analysed links of daily individual planning and dyadic planning with daily PA with two-level models with planning categories (*no planning, dyadic planning only, both individual and dyadic planning*, reference category: *individual planning only*) in their within-person and between-person components, as well as time, as fixed effects (uncontrolled model, see *Table 3*). At the *within-person level* we found that on days with *no planning* at all, participants performed significantly less PA, $b(SE) = -116.65(42.10)$, $p = .007$, than on days with individual planning only, in agreement with H1. Within-person *dyadic planning only* was not significantly linked with PA, not supporting H2. Here, it is important to consider that this category only held $n = 13$ observations (see *Figure 1*). On days with *both individual and dyadic planning*, however, participants were significantly more active, $b(SE) = 166.33(52.83)$, $p = .002$, than on days with individual planning only. Thus, H3 was supported. At the between-person level, we did not find any indication of *no planning, dyadic planning only, or both individual and dyadic planning* being significantly linked to total PA.

Sensitivity Analyses

To assess the robustness of our findings, we re-ran the analyses including covariates (see *Supplementary material S5*). Results of sensitivity analysis were comparable to the

uncontrolled model results reported above. We then re-ran the analyses excluding pre-obese participants whose BMI was below the threshold for obesity ($n = 4$; BMI 28.12 – 29.57 kg/m²).

Results were comparable with those for the full sample reported above, both in an uncontrolled and a controlled model (see *Supplementary material S6*).

Discussion

Daily individual planning and dyadic planning were assessed as strategies by persons with pre-obesity and obesity intending weight loss who had a consultation at an outpatient clinic for endocrinology. As predicted, we found support for within-person individual planning to be linked to more daily PA (as indicated by significantly higher MET min/day) compared to no planning at all. Dyadic planning was rarely used as sole strategy, and was not linked to more daily PA than individual planning, contrary to our hypotheses. However, we found that on days when individuals used dyadic planning in addition to individual planning, they were more physically active than on days when they only planned for themselves. None of the between-person planning predictors were significantly related to PA.

In line with theories of self-regulation such as the HAPA, and empirical findings on between-person effects (Carraro & Gaudreau, 2013; Sheeran et al., 2024), our findings confirmed higher daily PA on days when participants planned individually as compared to when they did not plan at all, supporting H1. Our participants reported individual planning on 59% of days, demonstrating this volitional, self-regulatory process for the majority of days. Our same-day finding is consistent with across-day effects reported by Berli, Lüscher, et al. (2018). They found previous-day individual planning, framed to refer to having planned how they would be active on the next day, to predict daily PA on the following day.

Dyadic planning was a less - but still fairly frequent feature on 31% of participants' days. It however mostly co-occurred with individual planning and, by itself, did not explain additional unique variance in daily PA. This is in contrast with H2, but supports H3. Dyadic planning seems to have been used as a complementary strategy to individual planning (Katzenelenbogen et al., 2022). The similarity of our findings to those by Katzenelenbogen et al. (2022), who studied self-selected goal pursuits as outcomes in a community sample of couples, strengthens the generalizability of our findings in a sample of persons with pre-obesity or obesity who planned dyadically with self-chosen planning partners. To the best of our

knowledge, our results provide the first evidence of dyadic planning of PA as a relevant social exchange process on a day-to-day basis for individual behaviour change in persons with pre-obesity or obesity.

Theoretically, dyadic planning would be especially helpful if it could compensate for low individual self-regulation capabilities (Keller et al., 2015), both dispositional as well as momentary. With our null findings of dyadic planning as a sole strategy, our findings cannot clearly support this compensatory effect. One explanation of the finding of co-occurrence could be that participants also adapted their individual plans after planning together with a planning partner: Discussions during dyadic planning conversations with a romantic partner, a friend, or a different partner, e.g. a parent, on what activity would be enjoyable, fit the schedule, weather, and be overall feasible for today for the target person, could have produced re-evaluations and new ideas which could have been relevant for plans the individuals made for themselves. Individual planning might have been revised after dyadic planning.

An additional explanation could come from the Systemic-Transactional Model (Bodenmann, 2005). Examining the temporal process of coping in couples, Bodenmann (2005) assumed that dyadic coping efforts would most frequently be used after the execution and failure of individual coping efforts. Keller et al. (2015) studied trajectories of individual and dyadic planning of rehabilitative exercises of patients following radical prostatectomy across eight months and found sequential patterns for each type of planning. Individual planning was associated steadily with rehabilitative exercises. Associations of dyadic planning and rehabilitative exercises strengthened with time. This could indicate a sequential use of strategies, with partner involvement showing effects only later in the process of rehabilitative exercise maintenance. Our daily diary study also found stable individual planning and fluctuating dyadic planning patterns.

To date, the daily occurrence of dyadic planning has predominantly been studied among couples from the general population with regards to different goal pursuits. We studied

spontaneous daily dyadic planning for PA specifically in a sample of persons with pre-obesity or obesity who entered a healthcare setting and allowed our assessments to capture processes of planning with varying partners. Despite these differences, findings were similar to those for couples. The finding that on days when participants planned both individually as well as dyadically points towards synergistic effects of planning alone and with a planning partner. There was substantial variation due to within-person differences in planning. As described above, the dyadic planning addition could be especially helpful in times of need, represented by the within-person effect. Between-person predictor variables were insignificant. Following the ideas on sequential execution of the planning strategies, it seems reasonable that people who often plan dyadically in addition to individually could frequently encounter self-regulatory failure. In this case, between-person level dyadic planning would be unlikely to be a predictor which could explain non-significant results of the between-person level variables.

With an average 641.72 MET-min/day, and 4492.03 MET-min/week of self-reported PA, our sample was quite active. While the PA-level across a whole week is similar to total PA reports from a Swiss cohort sample with 4774 MET-min/week in the 7-day recall IPAQ (Wanner et al., 2016), daily diary assessments, and samples with obesity often displayed lower amounts of PA in the literature (Bergh et al., 2017; Hagströmer et al., 2006). One possible explanation of our quite active sample is the timing of the assessment period which started just after an appointment at the outpatient clinic. Motivation for health-promoting PA might have been particularly high. Also, high estimates can be expected from self-report PA questionnaires when these are aggregated scores of “total physical activity” across life domains, including background activities such as work or housekeeping (Bauman et al., 2009). This could explain our high daily score.

Strengths and Limitations

Whereas the present study had several strengths such as an intensive-longitudinal design that can limit recall bias and allows for the examination of within-person and between-

person effects and had high external validity, there are some limitations. One limitation is that analyses were conducted with self-reported PA as an outcome. Self-reports have been found to overestimate PA (Conway et al., 2002). Our approach to check for the impact of this bias was comparing the three days of SenseWear device energy expenditure assessment to the self-reported diary responses. We found them to be moderately correlated. This is in line with prior findings such as Wanner et al. (2016)'s of a moderate correlation for total PA assessed by the self-report IPAQ questionnaire and accelerometer data. This gave us some confidence in our self-report measure.

Lastly, our design did not allow us to explore other avenues of research that would complement the findings. We did not control for relationship quality with the planning partner, who could - due to the assessment format - change from day to day. Relationship quality had been found as a relevant moderator of the effect of dyadic planning in couples (Keller et al., 2020; Knoll et al., 2017). Also, we did not capture the dyadic perspective of the planning partner from daily diaries. Including social relationships into the PA-promotion can also create a spill-over effect from which not only the target person, but also a planning partner could benefit (Keller et al., 2020; Kulis et al., 2025).

Despite these limitations, our research provides a first view on daily planning processes, alone and with somebody else, for PA in persons with pre-obesity or obesity intending weight loss after a consultation at an outpatient clinic.

Practical Implications

The findings have some implications for practice. Dyadic planning may be a relevant complementary strategy to individual planning in a patient sample. As such, it could be a potentially modifiable target for future interventions to support individuals pursuing behaviour change. Dyadic planning could help to provide a clear format to promote solution-focussed conversations and planning among two people wanting to help one person to achieve health-related behavioural goals.

Conclusion

The results of this research provide supporting evidence that planning is a relevant dynamic process in daily PA in persons with pre-obesity or obesity. The present study contributes to a growing body of evidence that dyadic planning may be a complementary strategy to individual planning.

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Tables

Table 1

Means, Standard Deviations, and Intraclass Correlations of Daily Physical Activity (MET-Mins/Day, Winsorized 5th/95th Percentile), and Dyadic Planning and Individual Planning Scales

Variables	Range	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	% missing	ICC	Repeated-measures correlations	
						Daily physical activity	Dyadic planning
Daily physical activity	0-1878	641.72	511.08	12.80	.48		
Dyadic planning	1-6	1.93	1.60	18.80	.35	.25***	
Individual planning	1-6	2.72	1.85	8.86	.39	.33***	.52***

Note. Observations $825 \leq n \leq 926$, sample size $117 \leq n \leq 127$ due to missing values and dropouts. Percent missings from total observations of $127 \times 8 = 1016$. ICC = Intraclass Correlation Coefficient; MET = Metabolic Equivalent of Task.

*** $p < .001$.

Table 2

Change Models of Daily Physical Activity (MET-Mins/Day, Winsorized 5th/95th Percentile), and Dyadic Planning and Individual Planning Scales

Variables	Fixed Effects Estimates (SE)						Random Effects Estimates (SE)									
	Intercept	<i>p</i>	TIME	<i>p</i>	TIME ²	<i>p</i>	Intercept	<i>p</i>	TIME	<i>p</i>	TIME ²	<i>p</i>	Level-1 Residual	<i>p</i>	AR1-rho	<i>p</i>
Daily physical activity	578.40 (38.91)	<.001	28.83 (22.74)	.207	-2.30 (3.16)	.469	73,726.53 (27,903.11)	.008	11,579.40 (9,402.36)	.218	234.49 (179.48)	.191	134,044.30 (11,754.84)	<.001	.14 (.06)	.021
Dyadic planning	2.14 (0.15)	<.001	-0.22 (0.08)	.006	0.03 (0.01)	.003	1.18 (0.39)	.002	0.08 (0.11)	.489	0.001 (0.002)	.674	1.63 (0.17)	<.001	.18 (.08)	.015
Individual planning	2.49 (0.15)	<.001	0.12 (0.08)	.125	-0.01 (.01)	.329	1.22 (0.31)	<.001	0.02 (0.01)	.056	-	-	2.02 (0.14)	<.001	.10 (.05)	.070

Note. $825 \leq n \leq 926$ observations, $120 \leq n \leq 127$ individuals, due to missing values and dropouts. MET = Metabolic Equivalent of

Task; *SE* = Standard Error; Dyadic planning and individual planning refer to a daily and spontaneous formation of plans about physical activity.

Table 3

Parameter Estimates from Uncontrolled Mixed Model Testing Daily Planning and its Link with Daily Physical Activity (MET-Mins/Day, Winsorized 5th/95th Percentile)

Fixed effects	<i>B (SE)</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI
Intercept	597.72 (40.31)	<.001	518.26; 677.18
Linear time ^a (reference = day 1)	13.92 (6.70)	.039	0.72; 27.13
Planning (reference = IP only)			
Within-person effects			
No planning	-116.65 (42.10)	.007	-200.62; -32.69
DP only	-101.99 (119.37)	.394	-337.18; 133.20
IP + DP	166.33 (52.83)	.002	60.99; 271.68
Planning (reference = IP only)			
Between-person effects			
No planning	-189.39 (137.99)	.173	-462.84; 84.05
DP only	-195.11 (564.60)	.730	-1311.59; 921.36
IP + DP	137.79 (130.27)	.293	-120.40; 395.99
Random effects ([co-]variances)	<i>Var (SE)</i>	<i>p</i>	95% CI
Level-2 (between-person)			
Intercept	97,671.10 (17,791.46)	<.001	68,346.12; 139,578.43
Linear time ^a (reference = day 1)	-	-	-
Planning (reference = IP only)			
Within-person effects			
No planning	14,573.01 (20,146.33)	.469	970.09; 218,919.90
DP only	-	-	-
IP + DP	44,083.91 (31,792.94)	.166	10,725.08; 181,200.53
Intercept and no planning	-16,889.54 (14,419.90)	.241	-45,152.02; 11,372.93
Intercept and IP + DP	15,789.13 (18,291.88)	.388	-20,062.29; 51,640.56
No planning and IP + DP	-11,038.47 (21,196.60)	.603	-52,583.04; 30,506.10
Level-1 (within-person)			
Residual	130,196.83 (9,570.66)	<.001	112,727.35; 150,373.57
Autocorrelation	.18 (.05)	.001	.07; .28

Note. 760 observations, 117 individuals. This restricted model does not control for between-person covariates (for fully-controlled model, see *Supplementary Material S5*). Unstandardized coefficients are displayed. Parameter estimates with significant *p*-values are printed in bold. MET = metabolic equivalent of task; *SE* = Standard Error; CI = confidence interval with lower level and upper level; Var = Variance; reference = reference category; IP = individual planning; DP = dyadic planning; Dyadic planning and individual planning refer to a daily and spontaneous

formation of plans about physical activity.

^a Centered on day 1 (0 = *day 1*, 1 = *day 2*, ...)

Figures

Figure 1*Frequency of Physical Activity-Related Planning in Daily Diary Days*

Note. Frequency of four categories of spontaneous planning among daily diary entries (824 observations, 52 missing values). Combined categories from dichotomized scores for individual planning and dyadic planning are *no planning* (i.e., no individual and no dyadic planning), *individual planning only* (i.e., individual, but not dyadic planning), *dyadic planning only* (i.e., dyadic, but not individual planning), and *both individual planning and dyadic planning* (i.e., individual and dyadic planning).

Statement of Contribution

What is already known on this subject?

- Individual planning is a powerful strategy to be more active in everyday life.
- Transactive goal dynamics theory posits others can extend individual self-regulation resources.
- It is unclear if planning one's behaviour with somebody else (e.g., dyadic planning) adds to individual planning.

What does this study add?

- Daily planning happens both individually as well as dyadically.
- Daily dyadic planning rarely occurs on its own without individual planning.
- Daily links to being active were strongest when both individual and dyadic planning were applied.